

Emotional Intelligence of Teachers and Classroom Learning Environment of Public Elementary Schools in Panabo City Division

Amor O. Estilo*

The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Philippines

Abstract— Emotional intelligence of teachers is believed to have influenced on developing a positive classroom learning environment. However, this had never been explored in the local context. With this, the study determined the extent of emotional intelligence of teachers and the classroom learning environment of public elementary schools in Panabo City Division. Also, it investigated the association of the involved variables. With the use of probability sampling, 150 elementary teachers in the public schools were selected as the respondents. Utilizing the descriptive-correlational survey method, the data collated were analyzed through the use of Mean and Product-Moment correlation. Results revealed that there was a high level of emotional intelligence among teachers and a high level of classroom learning environment. Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between the two variables. Based on the findings, it was further suggested that higher officials in the Department of Education and school principals may identify means on how to help teachers strengthen their emotional intelligence in order to develop a positive classroom learning environment. Apparently, the entire school need to work together to attain a healthy classroom learning environment.

Index Terms— Emotional intelligence, Classroom learning environment, Descriptive correlation, Panabo city division, Philippines.

1. Introduction

A classroom learning environment is more than just a classroom. It is a space in which students feel safe and supported in their pursuit of knowledge, as well as inspired by their surroundings. A place that serves as an avenue for students to showcase their potentials, talents, and skills. Definitely, it is one of the safest places where they acquire knowledge and skills regardless of their background and culture. This place serves as students' haven. This is the only place where students could socialize and express themselves with no inhibitions and apprehensions to be judged. Unfortunately, not all classroom learning environment meets the expectation of the students and parents.

In Turkey, it is seen that teachers have various problems in education contexts where students from different cultures come together. Teachers are observed to have insufficient teaching experience, time and classroom management, discipline. More so, teachers' poor attitudes towards students affect learning-

teaching processes negatively. More so, teachers do not have a specific curriculum to manage the learning-teaching process in a classroom environment where different cultures coexist poses a major problem for them [1]. In most developing countries of the world, today's classroom environment is characterized by large classes, deteriorating classroom buildings, poor lighting and seating conditions, interrupted power supply, insufficient supply of instructional resources/materials, faulty time-tabling, disinterestedness on the part of learners, lack of motivation on the part of teachers, and so on. It makes one wonder if learners are actually experiencing learning that will lead to the kind of understanding of science needed by all citizens [2].

In the Philippines, a study conducted revealed that with respect to classrooms, there had been progress in decongesting schools, but spatial inequality in classroom-student ratio exists and must be addressed. Spatial inequality is evident given the congested classrooms in some administrative regions. Moreover, additional classrooms are needed given that school buildings in certain remote areas do not meet quality and safety standards, enrolment is increasing, and existing classrooms deteriorate due to wear and tear and calamities. With respect to water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) facilities, the gaps are huge and become more visible when benchmarked against other countries [3].

In the Division of Panabo City, the classroom learning environment is not that well-ventilated. This somehow affects the learning of the students. More so, there are still overcrowded classrooms. In fact, maximum number of students in the class reaches to 60 students. Classroom learning environment is not fully equipped with facilities and instructional materials which affect teachers' instructional practices and learning among students. More so, teachers have been bombarded with so many reports affecting their means of addressing students who have individual indifferences. However, these were purely observations and had not been academically explored by means of research. This somehow picked the researcher's interest on how does the emotional intelligence of teachers affect the classroom learning environment.

Given these situations, the researcher explored the extent of

*Corresponding author: benchomblero@gmail.com

emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment in the public elementary schools in Panabo City Division since these variables had never been explored in the local context. Apart from determining the extent of emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment, this study investigated the association of the involved variables.

In this academic endeavor, the researcher shed light regarding emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment. This undertaking also hoped to provide insights to the DepEd officials and school leaders in crafting policies, programs, interventions, projects, activities that would strengthen teachers' emotional intelligence and classroom learning environment.

This study was mainly anchored to Emotional Intelligence (EI) which was initially proposed as an organized theory of emotional abilities [4] and was popularized in the general media leading to the model of emotional capacities [5]. These two models of EI were presented in the context of educational leadership. The first model [4] is the ability-model that considers four major emotion skill sets (perception, facilitation, understanding and managing). The second model [5] organizes EI competencies across two dimensions: capacities (emotion recognition and regulation) and application domains (toward self and others). There is some overlap between these models with regard to emotional perception (recognition) and regulation (managing).

Emotionally intelligent teachers show care for students, create emotional climate in classroom that develops the student learning environment and helps the teachers to become more effective to ensure academic achievement. It has been seen that teacher's emotional intelligence affects their comfort level, self-efficacy, job satisfaction level and enhances social relationship with students. As a result, emotional intelligence directly affects the teaching and learning process [6]. Working on classroom emotions has become vital now-a-days for students' emotional positive growth or for positive academic achievement. It is hoped that the successful teachers have high level of emotional competencies. Emotional intelligence forecast positive and successful results in all fields of life and consequently it dominates all fields of education. Teachers need to be trained in emotional intelligence to manage their own emotions for helping students. This makes emotional intelligence has become important for both teachers and students [7].

The role of emotional intelligence is very prodigious in educational field and in teaching. Emotional intelligence helps the teachers to understand their students in a better way. Teachers can make a pedagogical strategy to know the needs of and set goals for their students. In emotional intelligence, empathy is the main idea or concept for teaching and it is significant for the teachers to communicate with students to understand the background and culture of the students. During teaching of different subjects in classroom, motivation and social skills related to emotional intelligence are very helpful for teachers to establish their goals. To improve the social and personal life skills, emotional intelligence can help the students and teachers to enhance their achievements. The educational

institutes who give training and conduct seminars for developing emotional intelligence in teachers produce happier more, experienced and mature students for professional life [8].

2. Methodology

A. Research Design

This study was a quantitative research approach utilizing the descriptive correlational approach. Quantitative research deals with quantifying and analyzing variables in order to get results. It involves the utilization and analysis of numerical data using specific statistical techniques to answer questions like who, how much, what, where, when, how many, and how. It also describes the methods of explaining an issue or phenomenon through gathering data in numerical form. The study further reveals that quantitative methods can be categorized into; survey research, correlational research, experimental research and causal-comparative research [9]. Moreover, a descriptive correlation study is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing the relationships between variables without attempting to establish a causal relationship [10].

This study was considered as quantitative since it depended on the statistical figures when analyzing and interpreting the data. It was descriptive since its purpose was to determine the level of emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment. In addition, this academic pursuit was correlational since its purpose was to measure the connection between emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment in the selected public elementary schools in Panabo City Division.

B. Research Respondents

This study catered the 150 public elementary teachers in the Division of Panabo City. It was claimed that for simple regression analysis, it needs at least 50 samples and generally 100 samples for most research situations [11]. Hence, the 150 respondents were enough to address the purpose of this study.

In the inclusion and exclusion criteria, elementary teachers with at least two years teaching experience were chosen in this endeavor since their two years stay in the public school would help them to assess their emotional intelligence being in the public and the classroom learning environment. Respondents who felt awkward and uncomfortable in answering the survey questionnaire were free to withdraw from their participation. They were not forced to be part of the study. Their decision to withdraw was respected. Apparently, the respondents' welfare was given utmost importance in the conduct of the study.

C. Research Instruments

In gathering data, this study utilized an adapted survey questionnaire. The questionnaire that was utilized in this undertaking was divided into two sets. The first set was focusing on emotional intelligence of teachers while the second set was about the classroom learning environment.

The emotional intelligence questionnaire consisted of 20 items [12]. It has the following indicators, namely: self-awareness (1-5); self-management (1-5); social awareness (1-5); and relational transparency (1-5). For reliability, the

questionnaire was subjected to a pilot testing gaining a result of .77, suggesting that the items have relatively *high* internal consistency.

The classroom learning environment questionnaire comprised of 56 items [13]. It has the following indicators, namely: student cohesiveness (1-8); teacher support (1-8); involvement (1-8); task orientation (1-8); cooperation (1-8); equity (1-8); and differentiation (1-8). The questionnaire was subjected to a pilot testing having a result of .74 suggesting that the items have relatively *high* internal consistency.

The instruments in this study were contextualized to achieve the purpose of this study. The researcher incorporated all the comments and suggestions of the adviser, panel members and expert validators for the refinement of the tools and to achieve construct validity.

3. Results

Table 1
Summary on the level of emotional intelligence of teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Self-Awareness	3.45	High
2	Self-Management	4.28	Very High
3	Social Awareness	4.29	Very High
4	Relationship Management	4.30	Very High
Overall		4.08	High

Table 1 provides the summary on the level of emotional intelligence of teachers. It is exhibited that the overall mean of emotional intelligence of teachers is 4.08, which is in a high level. This means that emotional intelligence of teachers is oftentimes evident.

Data show that all four (4) indicators reveal a varying result ranging from high to very high result. As arranged chronologically, relationship management has the highest mean score (4.30). This is followed by social awareness (4.29), self-management (4.28), and self-awareness (3.45).

The data underscores a notable range of emotional intelligence among teachers across all four indicators, with varying degrees of strength from high to very high. Notably, when examined chronologically, it becomes evident that teachers excel the most in relationship management. Overall, these findings imply that while teachers exhibit remarkable competence in various dimensions of emotional intelligence, a particular focus on enhancing self-awareness could contribute to a more holistic and finely tuned emotional skill set, ultimately enriching their interactions with students and colleagues and further elevating the quality of the educational experience they provide.

With the high level of emotional intelligence, this reaffirmed the widely held belief that better levels of emotional well-being, professional performance, teacher-student relationships, and

students' academic achievement are seen in teachers who are emotionally intelligent [14]. Some researchers even go as far as attributing teaching to an emotional process as teachers have to be able to manage and keep their feelings in check in order to make their teaching more effective, as well as to inspire students and create a conducive environment for learning.

In the same vein, it was asserted that emotionally intelligent individuals can help others become more productive and successful too [15]. In fact, a developed hypothesis emphasized that teachers' emotional intelligence is positively related to student academic achievement [16]. However, it was argued that the current academic training for teachers has not integrated this emotional education construct [17].

Table 2
Summary on the level of classroom learning environment

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Student Cohesiveness	4.31	Very High
2	Teacher Support	4.33	Very High
3	Involvement	3.32	Moderately High
4	Task Orientation	3.32	Moderately High
5	Cooperation	3.36	Moderately High
6	Equity	4.35	Very High
7	Differentiation	4.16	High
Overall		3.89	High

Table 2 provides the summary on the level of classroom learning environment. It is exhibited that the overall mean of classroom learning environment is 3.89, which is in a high level. This means that classroom learning environment is oftentimes evident.

Data show that all seven (7) indicators reveal a varying result ranging from high to very high level. As arranged chronologically, equity has the highest mean score (4.35). This is followed by teacher support (4.33), student cohesiveness (4.31), differentiation (4.16), cooperation (3.36), and both involvement and task orientation (3.32).

The data underscores a consistently strong and supportive classroom learning environment across all seven indicators, with results spanning from high to very high levels. Collectively, these findings imply the establishment of a holistic learning environment that prioritizes fairness, fosters strong relationships between students and teachers, and promotes a sense of community and individualized learning.

The favorable findings of this study are aligned to the description that 'learning environment' as a variety of concepts related to teacher behavior, both in terms of instruction and other interactions in the classroom. It also involves classroom assessment practices, classroom materials, and the physical and atmospheric conditions of a school or classroom that may impact students' experiences and learning [18].

Relevant to the findings of the study, it was pointed out that

Table 3
Significance of the relationship between emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment

Emotional Intelligence of Teachers	Dependent Variable	r-value	p-value	Decision on Ho
Self-Awareness	Classroom Learning Environment	0.466	0.000	Rejected
Self-Management		0.479	0.000	Rejected
Social Awareness		0.487	0.000	Rejected
Relationship Management		0.495	0.000	Rejected
Overall		0.482*	0.000	Rejected

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

learning environments in the modern day embrace constructivist learning approaches, placing students at the center of the learning process. In line with constructivism, they promote the creation of knowledge and cooperative work, view educators as facilitators and mentors [19].

Presented in Table 3 are the data on the significance of the relationship between emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment. Reflected in the hypothesis, the relationship was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The overall r-value of .482 with a p-value of <0.05 signified the rejection of the null hypothesis. It means that there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment. This shows that emotional intelligence of teachers is correlated classroom learning environment.

Doing a pairwise correlation among the measures of both variables, it can be gleaned that self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management revealed computed r-values of 0.466, 0.479, 0.487, and 0.495 respectively with p-values which are less than 0.05 in the level of significance. This implies that as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management increases, the classroom learning environment also increases.

The result is in consonance to the study conducted emphasizing that emotional intelligence of teachers has a profound influence on the classroom learning environment, yielding notable effects on students' educational experiences. High emotional intelligence enables teachers to cultivate positive relationships with students, establishing a supportive and inclusive atmosphere conducive to learning [20].

In support, research indicated that teachers with higher levels of emotional intelligence are inclined towards integrating and compromising approaches when dealing with conflicts, thus constructively managing such conflicts in the classroom. Based on their findings, they recommend the incorporation of emotional skill programs into teachers' academic training to develop their emotional intelligence and equip them with the necessary tools for effective conflict management [21].

More so, it was emphasized that emotional intelligence has been shown to affect student learning behaviors, engagement, and academic performance. Teachers with high emotional intelligence can fixate on the emotional aspects of learning and teaching exchanges, a positive atmosphere in the classroom is directly produced which helps to make the course more interesting and enjoyable. Teachers with higher emotional intelligence are predisposed to adapting their teaching strategies to better suit the diverse, creative and unexpected opinions that students have in the classroom [14].

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered:

The extent of emotional intelligence of teachers implies that it is oftentimes evident. Specifically, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management are perceived to be always evident while self-awareness is oftentimes evident.

Meanwhile, the extent classroom learning environment is

oftentimes evident. In particular, teacher support and equity are perceived to be always evident while differentiation is oftentimes evident. On the other hand, involvement, task orientation, and cooperation are occasionally evident.

Based on the findings, emotional intelligence of teachers and classroom learning environment are correlated. Also, emotional intelligence of teachers significantly influences classroom learning environment. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

5. Recommendations

The following suggestions were offered based on the conclusions of the study:

The higher officials in the Department of Education may craft effective policies, programs, projects, interventions and activities which promote the emotional intelligence of teachers helping them to establish a positive classroom learning environment. They may create more initiatives that would further empower teachers' emotional intelligence which would pave a way also in helping students to be active participant in a healthy classroom environment.

Meanwhile, school principals may find means in crafting different programs and initiatives that would help them in assessing the status of their teachers' emotional intelligence. They may also assess themselves on how to help teachers in establishing a positive classroom learning environment specifically the kind of support that teachers need the most.

More so, teachers may take an effort to keep on upgrading themselves. They may attend various seminars, webinars, or any undertaking that would help them in strengthening their emotional intelligence. Also, teachers may also find means or strategies in developing a conducive learning environment for students. Lastly, future researchers may explore relevant information or other factors that would give additional inputs about emotional intelligence and classroom learning environment. They may consider using other research approaches such as qualitative research and mixed methods further explore the involved variables in this study.

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